

1 **Transcriptional changes during T-cell development.**

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6 We utilized genomic methods for systems biologic discovery and study of transcriptional events governing
7 lymphocyte development. We describe identification of stage-specific nuclear factor expression in the
8 lymphocyte maturation process at the thymus involving CD4 and CD8 single positive cells, including
9 factors important for switching in transcriptional programs and homeobox factors involved in lineage
10 specification, like *Lef1* which was absent in the cord blood and active only late in lineage specification
11 concomitant with *CD38* expression and seemingly contrary activation of *CD44* in mature CD8+ T-cells.
12 Another change reflecting critical stage-specific gene activation was developmentally-restricted expression
13 of genes encoded by the tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF) receptor (TNFR) superfamily in the CD8+
14 single positive mature cytotoxic T lineage: *TNFAIP3* and the inflammatory *TNFRSF1B* receptor.
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